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D2 - Good practice guide on the calibration of commercial SV enabled instrumentation with sampling rates up to 96 kSPS

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Glossary

TERM	DEFINITION
1PPS	One Pulse Per Second – A signal used for precise time synchronization, often generated by GPS receivers.
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter – A device that converts analog signals into digital data for processing.
ASDU	Application Service Data Unit – A data structure used in communication protocols to encapsulate application-level data.
CALIBRATION	The process of adjusting and verifying the accuracy of a measurement instrument by comparing it to a known standard.
DCA	Direct Current Ammeter – An instrument used to measure direct current in an electrical circuit.
DMM	Digital Multimeter – An electronic measuring instrument that combines several measurement functions in one unit.
DUT	Device Under Test – The equipment or component being tested in a laboratory or field setup.
GRANDMASTER CLOCK	The primary time source in a PTP network that distributes accurate time to all other devices.
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device – A microprocessor-based controller used in substations for protection, control, and monitoring.
LPIT	Low Power Instrument Transformer – A type of transformer that provides low power analog signals suitable for digital processing.
PHASE DISPLACEMENT	The angular difference between two waveforms, typically voltage and current, in an AC system.
POWER PROFILE	UTILITY A configuration of PTP designed specifically for power utility applications to ensure accurate time synchronization.
PTP	Precision Time Protocol – A protocol used to synchronize clocks throughout a computer network, defined in IEEE 1588.
RMS	Root Mean Square – A statistical measure of the magnitude of a varying quantity, commonly used in AC voltage and current measurements.
SAMU	Stand-Alone Merging Unit – Converts analog signals from conventional transformers into digital Sampled Values (SV) for IEC 61850 communication.
SAMPLE RATE	The number of samples taken per second from a continuous signal to convert it into a digital signal.
SAMPLE COUNT	The number of samples collected over a specific period or during a measurement process.

SAMPLED VALUE	A digital representation of an analog signal obtained by sampling at regular intervals.
SHUNTS	Low-resistance electrical components used to measure current by producing a voltage drop proportional to the current flow.
TESTBED	A test setup or environment used for validating and verifying the performance of electrical devices or systems.
UNCERTAINTIES	The range of possible error in a measurement, indicating the confidence level of the result.

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1 Summary

Digital substations are becoming a cornerstone of the future electrical energy transmission and distribution network. These substations rely heavily on digital instrumentation, served by instrumentation capable of producing Sampled Values (SV) in compliance with the IEC 61850 and IEC 61869 standards. Stand-alone Merging Units (SAMUs) are used to digitize analog signals from conventional instrument transformers and transmit these signals in real-time via Ethernet-based process buses. This makes it possible to combine existing and proven analog voltage and current sensors with digital measurement and protection devices.

With the introduction of SAMUs new calibration procedures and uncertainty estimation methods are needed to characterize these devices. Characteristics such as amplitude and phase displacement are extracted from the digital SAMUs SV streams and compared to a reference to determine the accuracy class. This is done on test beds that have been developed and calibrated for their gain and absolute phase relative to the 1PPS signal at various NMIs. In this work, the test benches that have been developed by the participating laboratories (NMIs and others) , a description of these testbenches and their performance can be found in the annex. During the development of these testbenches some important knowledge and pitfalls have been found and are shared.

The most important can be summarized in:

- The SAMU should be calibrated in the same way as it will be used.
- The correct configuration of the SAMU is important.
- If calibration of amplitude is made by comparing measurements of a wide-band RMS measuring reference with a Single-tone measuring device any distortion or noise of the signal may cause errors.

Therefore, this good practice guide provides a structured approach for configuring, testing, and validating the performance of these devices under real-world conditions. The report is concluded with a comparison of four testbenches from different NMIs. This comparison shows in general good equivalence but also shows that the calibration of a SAMU is not trivial.

2 Introduction

The ongoing transformation of the electric power sector, driven by the integration of renewable energy sources (RES), demands a more dynamic, flexible, and digital infrastructure for grid monitoring, control, and protection. In this context, digital substations are becoming a cornerstone of the future energy system, as recognized by strategic roadmaps such as those from ENTSO-E and the European Metrology Network for Smart Electricity Grids (EMN SEG). These substations rely heavily on digital instrumentation, especially instrument transformers and merging units capable of producing Sampled Values (SV) in compliance with the IEC 61850 and IEC 61869 standards.

Stand-alone Merging Units (SAMUs) play a pivotal role in this transition by digitizing analog signals from conventional instrument transformers and transmitting these signals in real-time via Ethernet-based process buses, providing the opportunity to still use already installed equipment but still digitalize the rest of the substation and controls. The precise and traceable performance of SAMUs is essential for the reliability of protection systems and the accuracy of measurements used for billing and grid management. However, the adoption of SV-enabled instrumentation introduces new metrological challenges. Existing calibration procedures and uncertainty estimation methods used for analog devices are not directly transferable to digital systems.

This Good Practice Guide was developed to address the lack of standardized procedures for the calibration of commercial SV-compatible devices, particularly SAMUs. Based on the experience of laboratories participating in the Digital-IT project, where the SAMUS accuracy class is verified using SV streams, characteristics such as amplitude and phase shift are extracted from the SAMU digitized signal, where the grounding mode and synchronization are a fundamental part of the SAMU calibration and operation process. Therefore, the guide provides a structured approach for configuring, testing, and validating the performance of these devices under real-world conditions. The guide covers comprehensive considerations regarding the test bench, signal generation, time synchronization, software configuration, and uncertainty analysis.

The aim of this document is to support National Metrology Institutes (NMIs), calibration laboratories, manufacturers, and utilities in establishing traceable and harmonized calibration procedures for digital substation equipment. By following the recommendations in this guide, stakeholders can ensure that SV-enabled devices meet performance requirements, support interoperability, and contribute to the robustness of future-proof, digitalized energy systems.

3 Stand Alone Merging Unit (SAMU) calibration

3.1 Normative framework

Figure 1 shows the relative positions of different standards with respect to each other in the measurement part (IEC 61869) and on the other hand the data flow for metering (IEC 62052 [1] & 62053 [2]), protection (IEC 60255), and switchgear (IEC 62271 [3]). The functionalities relevant to this document are in the IEC 61869 series, which defines the requirements for LPITs and SAMUs. Stand-Alone Merging Units (SAMUs) are used for transforming analog input signals and, rarely, proprietary digital outputs from ITs and LPITs into a standardized digital output. The SAMU standard IEC 61869-13 [4] refers to IEC 61869-9 [5] for data formatting and other aspects of the digital interface.

Figure 1. Position of different standards in the context of digital measuring and protection in an IEC 61850 substation environment

The SAMU standard IEC 61869-13 [4] inherits performance requirements from IEC 61869-1 [6]. It also supplements the standard by introducing a higher accuracy class for a SAMU (measuring class 0,05) in support of the most accurate IT and LPIT measurement classes. Protection rated inputs for a SAMU are also introduced in part 13, but testing the protection-related performance is outside the scope of this guide. The digital output, which is of interest in this review is defined in IEC 61869-9. It does not have any requirements for accuracy but does include some performance requirements for time synchronicity and digital output data latency.

Measuring and protection rated device often have significantly different design goals and performance requirements. In case of being rated for protection applications, LPITs in IEC 61869-9 [5] and SAMUs in IEC 61869-13 are required to also have a measuring class rating (clause 5.6 in IEC 61869-9/13). This is required due to protection class devices being often used also for measurement purposes.

An overview of all standards related to SAMU calibration can be found Table 1. Some standards are still under development (NP, CD).

Table 1. List of standards referred to in this document with their respective version.

Standard	Topic
IEC 60255	Measuring relays and protection equipment
IEC 61850-7-2:2010	Basic information and communication structure
IEC 61850-9-2:2011	Sampled values

IEC 61850-9-2 LE	Implementation guideline for IEC 61850-9-2
IEC 61850-9-3:2016	Power utility profile for PTP (IEEE 1588-2008)
IEC 61869	Instrument transformers
IEC 61869-1:2023	Instrument transformers - General requirements
IEC 61869-7 (NP)	Specific requirements for electronic Voltage Transformers, new work proposal, very early
IEC 61869-8 (CD)	Specific requirements for electronic Current Transformers, committee draft, most likely final
IEC 61869-9:2016	Digital interface for instrument transformers
IEC 61869-13:2021	Stand-alone merging unit (SAMU)
IEC 62052	Electricity metering equipment
IEC 62053-22:2020	Static meters for AC active energy
IEC 62271	High-voltage switchgear and control gear

3.2 Signal generation

3.2.1 Magnitude and phase

The strictest measurement class in IEC-61869 is the 0.05 % class. Considering the lowest and highest voltage and current options and the strictest class, this leads to the following specifications that must be met if all possible devices governed by this norm are to be calibrated:

- For currents between 20mA and 20A at the nominal frequency the current magnitude the error must be less than 0.05%, and for lower currents down to 5 mA the error must be less than 0.1%.
- For voltages between 6.7 V to 437 V at the nominal frequency the maximum voltage magnitude error is 0.05% and for lower voltages down to 667 mV the maximum magnitude error is 0.1 %.

The strictest phase error requirement is 2.5 minutes for nominal frequency, which corresponds to 1.9 us for 60 Hz. For harmonics the frequency is of course higher, but the requirements are less strict, making 1.9 us the strictest timing requirement. The ratio and phase errors are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Harmonic performance for the 0.05% class as defined in IEC-61869 (Table 1302).

Accuracy class (at f_R)	Ratio error at low frequency		Ratio error (±) at harmonics					Phase displacement (±) at low frequency	Phase error (±) at harmonics			
								Degrees	Degrees			
	0 Hz	1 Hz	2 nd to 4 th	5 th and 6 th	7 th to 9 th	10 th to 13 th	Above 13 th	1 Hz	2 nd to 4 th	5 th and 6 th	7 th to 9 th	10 th to 13 th
0,05	+0,5 % -100 %	+0,5 % -30 %	0,5 %	1 %	2 %	4 %	+4 % -100 %	45	0,5	1	2	4

NOTE 0 Hz in the first column means DC coupling is allowed but not required.

As shown in Table 2, the frequencies that need to be supplied are: 0 Hz (DC), 1 Hz, nominal frequency (50 Hz or 60 Hz) and the 2nd to 13th harmonic of this frequency (max. 780 Hz). Additionally, for the aliasing test a

nominal current (1 A or 5 A) with a high frequency is required. This can be either 3950 Hz, 3940 Hz, 12750 Hz or 12740 Hz.

The signal source needs to be carefully chosen to be able to supply these signals with low noise levels and low distortion, such that the resulting measurement uncertainty is lower than the maximum errors in the device class. A margin of 10x is recommended. The same principle applied to the phase stability. There are no requirements in the norm regarding the phase between voltage and current (power factor).

In this project, these nominal values were chosen as operating points: 100V, 1A, 50Hz and 60 Hz. From these values the calibration points are derived according to IEC-61869-9.

3.2.2 Wiring systems: poly-phase and single-phase

A MU usually has four inputs for voltage and four inputs for current. Three of the inputs are used to measure the voltage on L1, L2, and L3, while a fourth measures the neutral voltage. The same is true for the current channel. The neutral voltage and current are usually close to zero. Only when there is an imbalance between the phases will there be neutral voltage and/or current. However, this channel does need to be calibrated. It can either be done by applying an unbalanced polyphase signal or measuring the neutral input separately.

There are two strategies when calibrating a MU.

1. Calibrating each input separately, disconnecting or shorting the inputs that are not being measured
2. Calibrating all inputs simultaneously using a poly phase setup.

Since it is unknown how the MU works internally, the calibration should happen in the same configuration as its intended use. Usually this would be a polyphase setup.

It can be efficient to supply multiple inputs with the same signal, to calibrate them together. However, it is not recommended to put the current inputs in series as it might introduce errors due to common mode voltage on the current inputs. This is mainly visible in the phase displacement. When comparing a MU to the reference MU, the current inputs of the different MUs must be in series. The reference MU should be designed not to be affected by common mode voltage on the current input, so it can be connected to the high side of the current loop, ensuring the DUT MU has no common mode voltage on its current inputs.

Voltage inputs can be put in parallel, since IEC-61869 requires that crosstalk should be low enough to keep the device within specified accuracy limits. This means that any combination of channel input should not cause other channels errors to be outside the accuracy limits, although it can influence the measurement results. However, the norm does not specify a way to test this requirement. A calibration report should therefore report the used wiring system to ensure reproducibility. The crosstalk requirement also allows for current and voltage to be calibrated simultaneously. There are no requirements on the phase between voltage and current (power factor), so it can be inferred that the crosstalk requirement holds for any power factor.

Grounding of the input channels needs to be considered carefully to ensure no common mode voltage on the current inputs while avoiding ground loops and leakage of measurement current to ground. The MU current input high should be floating, and the current low should be grounded at the current source. The same holds for the voltage input.

3.2.3 Signal measurement: characterization and uncertainties

In this project, five approaches has been used for the calibration of SAMUs: 1) using another SAMU as reference as in the calibration setup of VTT and GUM, 2) using a commercial wattmeter as in the calibration setup of VSL, 3) using a PMU-calibrator as in the calibration setup of RISE, and 4) using a sampling DMM as a reference in the calibration setup of Metroser 5) using an absolute time as reference. Refer to Appendix A for further details about these approaches. For further details about the reference measurements, refer to [7]

- **Considerations on transducers**

It is recommended that transducers be characterized previously to the calibration as a function the following variables:

- Frequency response in amplitude and phase-displacement
- Error in the value of the scale factor, with corresponding uncertainty
- Temperature dependence of transducers

- **Considerations on the noise of the measured signal**

When the reference measurement is given by an instrument that measures the RMS value of the signal, the effect of the DC value and the broadband noise on the reference measurement needs to be quantified. Include these effects as uncertainty components in the uncertainty budget of the calibration of the SAMU.

- **Example of uncertainty estimation for calibration of SAMU**

The testbeds of four laboratories are described in Appendix A. An example of measurement uncertainty budget for the magnitude of the current in the range 20 – 100 mA, RMS at 50 Hz is presented in Table 4. This uncertainty budget corresponds to the calibration setup of RISE in Appendix A.

The model equation is:

$$\varepsilon = 100 \cdot \frac{I_{DUT} - I_{REF}}{I_{REF}} \quad [\%]$$

Where ε , I_{DUT} , and I_{REF} are the error in current magnitude of the device under test (DUT, i.e. the SAMU), the current magnitude read by the DUT, and the current magnitude read by the reference instrument, respectively. The expanded measurement uncertainty is evaluated using a coverage factor $k = 2$, corresponding to a confidence level of approximately 95.45%.

Table 3. Uncertainty budget for calibration of current magnitude in the range 20 – 100 mA, RMS at 50 Hz

Uncertainty component	Standard uncertainty (% of reading)
Traceability reference instrument	7.50E-03
Drift reference instrument	2.31E-05
Resolution of reading, reference instrument	2.89E-05
Variation in reading (type A), 4 degrees of freedom	1.51E-02
Uncorrected reference instrument	5.20E-03
Effect of the signal's DC-value on the reference reading	6.49E-03
Effect of the signal's high-frequency noise on the reference reading	2.89E-03
Expanded uncertainty (k = 2): 0.043 %	

3.3 Network

Depending on the type of equipment and manufacturer, there may be more than one communication bus that needs to be configured and connected to the corresponding IEDs. In SAMUs, the following characteristics can be found:

- **Station bus:** Typically allows for data reporting and equipment management.
- **Process bus:** Through which GOOSEs and SVs will be published and subscribed.
- **Synchronization reception via PTP.**
- **Redundancy:** HSR and/or PRP.

Some of the considerations to take into account regarding the network are the following

- To establish communication between the SAMU and other IEDs or with the computer, it is necessary to have a switch. If the SAMU synchronizes via PTP, it must support PTP synchronization traffic according to the "power profile" defined in IEEE C37.238-2017 [8] and "defined in utility profile" IEC 61850-9-3:2016 [9] standards. The synchronization parameters configuration must match those of the SAMU.
- Regarding communication buses, it is important to consider addressing, whether dynamic or static. However, it is recommended to separate the buses at the network level, as they offer better performance. VLANs are usually employed, which can be configured on the switch. This way, multicast traffic is separated from the rest.
- Regarding redundancy, in the case of equipment calibration, it is recommended not to activate it, as this reduces the number of IEDs required for configuration and setup.

3.4 Time synchronization (1PPS or PTP)

Preferred time synchronization method in IEC 61869-9 [5] is precision time protocol (PTP) defined in IEC 61588 [10]. As a legacy option, ensuring compatibility of IEC 61850-9-2LE compliant equipment, 1PPS is allowed. Both standards prefer an optical fiber transmission of the 1PPS signal, but in practice also electrical 1PPS pulses can be found in measurement and test equipment. The latter is preferred for test purposes since physical time standards often have electrical output for their 1PPS reference signals. Conversion from and to an optical time reference will also introduce a delay with an associated uncertainty. The requirement for timing uncertainty delivered to measurement equipment through means of 1PPS is respectively $\pm 2 \mu\text{s}$ and $\pm 1 \mu\text{s}$ in IEC 61850-9-2LE and IEC 61869-9 [5].

For PTP synchronization, the Power Utility Profile specified in IEC 61850-9-3 is required to be implemented in IEC 61869-9 [5] compliant equipment. The profile includes among other things a limited subset of PTP functionalities, standardized message exchanges rates, and synchronization inaccuracy budgets for different networking equipment. For example, the peer-delay mechanism is explicitly required to be implemented. Message exchange rates are set as one per second, including the time-critical Sync and PDelay_Req messages. Support for both 1-step and 2-step clock mechanisms is mandatory. The lack of a physical and tangible timing reference means relating the phase of the signal encoded into an SV stream to an instance of time, which by definition is the start of a UTC-aligned second, and in practice a rising edge in a 1PPS signal becomes difficult.

4 SAMU software configuration

In this section, some points related to the configuration that needs to be done through the manufacturer's software will be addressed.

4.1 Sampling rate and datasets

Table 4. Sample rates and data formatting for different applications in IEC 61869-9 [5]. Preferred sample rates are highlighted in *bold*.

Sample rate [Hz]	ASDUs per frame	Frame publishing rate [frames / s]	samples per nominal cycle		Remarks
			50 Hz	60 Hz	
4000	1	4000	80		protection application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 50 Hz systems
4800	1	4800		80	protection application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 60 Hz systems
4800	2	2400	96	80	Preferred rate for protection applications
5760	1	5760		96	60 Hz systems
12800	8	1600	256		measuring application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 50 Hz systems
14400	6	2400	288	240	Preferred rate for measuring applications
15360	8	1920		256	measuring application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 60 Hz systems
96000	1	96000			Preferred rate for high bandwidth DC application

According to IEC 61869-9, there is a dataset with predefined data that can be used to publish current and voltage data. Some manufacturers have it in their default configurations; this is PhsMeas1. If it is not defined, it can also be created depending on the manufacturer, maintaining the order presented below:

Table 5. Phsmeas1 dataset

Dataset	
DSName	PhsMeas1
Data	IATCTR1.AmpSV.instMag.i
	IATCTR1.AmpSV.q
	IBTCTR2.AmpSV.instMag.i
	IBTCTR2.AmpSV.q
	ICTCTR3.AmpSV.instMag.i
	ICTCTR3.AmpSV.q
	INTCTR4.AmpSV.instMag.i
	INTCTR4.AmpSV.q
	UATVTR1.VolSV.instMag.i
	UATVTR1.VolSV.q

	UBTVTR2.VolSV.instMag.i
	UBTVTR2.VolSV.q
	UCTVTR3.VolSV.instMag.i
	UCTVTR3.VolSV.q
	UNTVTR4.VolSV.instMag.i
	UNTVTR4.VolSV.q

It is important to mention that, according to the manufacturer, some signals that are part of the dataset can be configured as calculated. If necessary, PhsMeasxx(1-99) datasets can be created for the publication of measurements using sampled values (SV). The dataset must be assigned to a control block, remembering that SVs are multicast. The standard IEC-61869 establishes that the control block name (MSVCBName) must be assigned as MSVCBxx.

Table 6. Sv control block configuration

Attribute	Comments
Name	They will be assigned following the format MSVCBxx (1-99), where instances 1 and 2 are reserved as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MSVCB01 transmits sampled values at a rate of 80 samples per cycle, typically used for electrical protection applications. MSVCB02 transmits sampled values at a rate of 256 samples per cycle, typically used for power quality and measurements.
SV.Ena	If TRUE, the transmission of the SV buffer is activated; if FALSE, the transmission of the SV buffer is deactivated.
MSVID	It is used as an identifier and must be unique in the substation.
Addr	The values to be assigned are within the range 01-0C-CD-04-00-00 and 01-0C-CD-04-01-FF.
APPID	It can be assigned from 0x4000 to 0x7FFF. The default value is 0x4000.
PRIORITY	Default is 0. It can be assigned from 0 to 7.
VID	Default is 0. It can be assigned from 0 to 4095.

There are SAMUs in which the SmpRate is already predefined and specified in the manufacturer's manuals, while in others it can be configured. It is worth noting that this configuration can be done in samples per second or per cycle. The following notation is used by manufacturers to identify the configuration in samples per cycle.

$$F f S s I i U u$$

Where:

- f* is the digital output sample rate expressed in samples per second;
- s* is the number of ASDUs (samples) contained in a sampled value message;
- i* is the number of current quantities contained in each ASDU;

u is the number of voltage quantities contained in each ASDU.

For example,

- **4000S1U4I4**. Frame defined in IEC 61850-9-2 LE for protection in 50Hz systems. Only available in 50 Hz devices.
- **F4800S2U4I4**. Frame defined in IEC 61869-9: 2016 [5] for measurement and protection in 50 and 60 Hz systems.
- **F12800S8U4I4**. Frame defined in IEC 61850-9-2 LE for energy quality in 50 Hz systems. Only available in 50 Hz devices.

The IEC 61869-9 standard establishes the following SmpRate per cycle:

Table 7. Smprate according to IEC 61869-9 standard

SmpRate	Samples per cycle	ASDUS
4000	50Hz = 80	1
4800	50Hz = 96 60Hz=80	1
4800		2
5700	60Hz=96	1
12800	50Hz= 256	8
14400	50Hz= 288	6
15360	60Hz=256	8
96000	50Hz= 1960	1

4.2 Transform ratio and data precision

According to the 61869-9 standard, sampled values will be published in primary values, considering that currents are presented in milliamperes (scaling factor 0.001) and voltages in centivolts (scaling factor 0.01). Given that there is a transformation ratio for current and voltage, they can be represented as:

- Transformation ratio for current: Primary current / Secondary current
- Transformation ratio for voltage: Primary voltage / Secondary voltage.

There are manufacturers where it is necessary to configure the transformation ratio with a single value and others where the primary and secondary values must be configured.

It is important to note that, due to the units in which the data is published, in the case of calibration tests, it is advisable that the transformation ratio be a large integer to avoid losing data resolution.

4.3 Time synchronization configuration

For the proper functioning of the SAMU, it is necessary for it to be synchronized with a reliable time source. This configuration is usually done using the manufacturer's software, and there may be different options such as:

- PPS: 1 Pulse Per Second optical signal
- PTP: Precision Time Protocol
- IRIG-B

It is recommended to use the PPS or PTP options.

5 Testbed checklist

This is a list of the main points to check before starting a SAMUs calibration. If any of them do not apply to your testbed, please discard them.

RESULTS

NA = Not applicable

OK = Result as expected

NOK = Unfavorable result.

Table 8. Testbed checklist

EQUIPMENT VERIFICATION	RESULTS
Signal generator on	
Signal processing devices on	
Clocks on	
Switch on	
Equipment with algorithms for amplitude/phase calculation on	
VERIFYING PTP CONFIGURATION	
The clock has PTP synchronization enabled	
The switch has PTP synchronization enabled	
All IEDs that need PTP synchronization have it enabled in their configuration	
The PTP version published by the clock and the switch is the one required by the SAMU and the rest of the equipment that needs PTP synchronization	
The domain number of the clock and switch is the same as that of all IEDs that need PTP synchronization	
The type of clock configured in the SW must be supported by the SAMU and the rest of the IEDs that need PTP synchronization	
NETWORK CONNECTION VERIFICATION	
If the SAMU has fiber connectors, ensure that the speed, connector type, and mode are the same on both ends of the SAMU and the switch, and that the connected fiber optic cable matches the connector type. These considerations also apply to the PPS clock connected to the SAMU.	
Verify that the SAMU and the device with amplitude/phase calculation algorithms are on the same network. You can use a traffic analyzer to view the SAMU's SV on the device.	
If you're using a network-controlled signal generator, verify that it's connected to the network with the computer that hosts your software. Ping the generator.	
For PTP synchronization, verify that the clock is on the same network as the SAMU and any other devices that require it. Use a traffic analyzer to verify the existence of PTP traces	

<p>For PPS synchronization, verify that there is a connection between the clock and the SAMU through the PPS port. You can verify synchronization in the device's software. If not, check the cable types and ensure the clock is receiving a PPS pulse.</p>																																				
<p>If the device with amplitude/phase calculation algorithms requires synchronization, verify that it is connected to a network with a clock that corresponds to PTP or NTP. Ping the NTP server from the device or check the PTP traces on the device.</p>																																				
<p>VERIFYING SAMU CONFIGURATION USING NETWORK ANALYZER</p>																																				
<p>Verify that you see SV traces. This is the view in Wireshark.</p>																																				
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<p>Use a traffic analyzer to verify that the APPID is the one configured on the SAMU. In the example, the APPID is 0x4005 in the configuration (using the SAMU software or the ICD).</p>																																				

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<p>Verify that the SmpRate matches the configured rate and the rate published by the SAMU. Using the signal analyzer, locate smpCnt = 0 and the previous rate. This way, you can verify it. This is an example for SmpRate 4000.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="159 1198 1228 1332"> <thead> <tr> <th>No.</th> <th>Time</th> <th>Source</th> <th>Destination</th> <th>Protocol</th> <th>Length</th> <th>smpSynch</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>200788</td> <td>15:32:56,999879</td> <td>Ar...</td> <td>Iec-Tc57_04:00:05</td> <td>IEC61850 Sampled Values</td> <td>127</td> <td>global</td> </tr> <tr> <td>200789</td> <td>15:32:57,000130</td> <td>Ar...</td> <td>Iec-Tc57_04:00:05</td> <td>IEC61850 Sampled Values</td> <td>127</td> <td>global</td> </tr> <tr> <td>200791</td> <td>15:32:57,000421</td> <td>Ar...</td> <td>Iec-Tc57_04:00:05</td> <td>IEC61850 Sampled Values</td> <td>127</td> <td>global</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Frame 200789: 127 bytes on wire (1016 bits), 127 bytes captured (1016 bits) > Ethernet II, Src: Artecheg_ff:f0:70 (00:1a:0f:ff:f0:70), Dst: Iec-Tc57_04:00:05 (00:07:0d:00:00:05) ✓ IEC61850 Sampled Values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> APPID: 0x4005 Length: 113 > Reserved 1: 0x0000 (0) Reserved 2: 0x0000 (0) ✓ savPdu <ul style="list-style-type: none"> noASDU: 1 ✓ seqASDU: 1 item <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ASDU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> svID: arteche_samu_05 smpCnt: 3999 <table border="1" data-bbox="1117 1355 1228 1579"> <tbody> <tr><td>0000</td><td>01</td></tr> <tr><td>0010</td><td>00</td></tr> <tr><td>0020</td><td>0f</td></tr> <tr><td>0030</td><td>82</td></tr> <tr><td>0040</td><td>ff</td></tr> <tr><td>0050</td><td>03</td></tr> <tr><td>0060</td><td>ff</td></tr> <tr><td>0070</td><td>ff</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	smpSynch	200788	15:32:56,999879	Ar...	Iec-Tc57_04:00:05	IEC61850 Sampled Values	127	global	200789	15:32:57,000130	Ar...	Iec-Tc57_04:00:05	IEC61850 Sampled Values	127	global	200791	15:32:57,000421	Ar...	Iec-Tc57_04:00:05	IEC61850 Sampled Values	127	global	0000	01	0010	00	0020	0f	0030	82	0040	ff	0050	03	0060	ff	0070	ff	
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```

> Frame 200791: 127 bytes on wire (1016 bits), 127 bytes captured (1016 bits)
> Ethernet II, Src: ArtechG_ff:f0:70 (00:1a:0f:ff:f0:70), Dst: Iec-Tc57_04:00
< IEC61850 Sampled Values
  APPID: 0x4005
  Length: 113
  > Reserved 1: 0x0000 (0)
  Reserved 2: 0x0000 (0)
  < savPdu
    noASDU: 1
    < seqASDU: 1 item
      < ASDU
        svID: arteche_samu_05
        smpCnt: 0
        confRev: 1
        smpSynch: global (2)
    
```

Verify that the ASDUS number is correct for the data transfer rate (SmpRate). According to 61869-9. This is an example for a data transfer rate of 12800.

SmpRate	ASDUS
4000	1
4800	1
4800	2
5700	1
12800	8
14400	6
15360	8
96000	1

```

< IEC61850 Sampled Values
  APPID: 0x4004
  Length: 803
  > Reserved 1: 0x0000 (0)
  Reserved 2: 0x0000 (0)
  < savPdu
    noASDU: 8
    < seqASDU: 8 items
      < ASDU
        svID: arteche_samu_04
        smpCnt: 0
        confRev: 1
        smpSynch: global (2)
      > PhsMeas1
    > ASDU
    
```

CHECKING THE CONNECTIONS BETWEEN THE SAMU AND THE GENERATOR

For current amplitude tests, verify that the generator is connected directly to the corresponding current input.

For voltage amplitude tests, verify that the generator is connected directly to the corresponding voltage input.

VERIFICATION OF SV VOLTAGE MAGNITUDES

Perform a current injection and verify with an SV voltage analyzer that the injected magnitude corresponds to the expected value, considering that SV voltages are measured on the primary side and the equipment's transformation ratio. For example, if the current transformer ratio is 1 and 1 A is injected, the effective value of SV current will measure 1 A.

Perform a voltage injection and verify with an SV voltage analyzer that the injected magnitude corresponds to the expected value, considering that SV voltages are measured

on the primary side and the equipment's transformation ratio. For example, if the voltage transformer ratio is 1 and 1 V is injected, the rms value of the SV voltages will read 1 V.	
Verify in the configuration that there are no calculated signals, as the injected value will not correspond with the value published by the SAMU through the SV.	
For phase calculations, if attenuators are used, verify that the current/voltage is as expected at the measurement device and remains equal to that generated at the SAMU input.	
For phase calculations, if amplifiers are used between the digitizer and the SAMU, verify that the current/voltage is as expected at the SAMU input.	

6 Sampled Values analysis. Software requirements

The stream of Sampled Values stream must be received and processed to check the validity of the data and extract the parameters that give the measurement value. Concerning to the acquisition step, a standard tool as tcpdump, thsark or wireshark can be used. Next, the data can be processed to convert the acquisition format (pcap in the case of the previous examples) to other format and/or check the validity of the stream. Finally, if the data pass all control checks, the parameter of magnitude or phase can be extracted from the Sampled Values stream. These steps are covered in the next subsections.

6.1 Sampled Values stream validity

The Sampled Values stream should fulfil some requirements to be used as a source of the measurement data.

- **Quality flag:** The IEC 61850-9-2 [11] establish a mechanism (and the IEC 61869-9 enforces it) to mark every piece of data with a quality flag describing its quality. The standards state that a quality field with value zero means the data contained in this field is normal. The software should check that all data used in a measurement are correct, so the quality is zero for all of them.
- **Frame loss detection:** Given the fact that the sampled value stream doesn't have delivery check nor retransmission, the software is responsible for the detection of frame loss. This can be done by testing the continuity of the smpCnt field, detecting losses when gaps are observed.
- **smpSynch:** The time synchronization is a requirement established in IEC 61869-9 [5] and is especially relevant for the computation of the phase displacement, given the fact that it should be computed the absolute phase of the waveform and compare it with the absolute phase of input. In that way, checking the status of synchronization is a way to check the reported synchronization status of the SAMU. Only the data reported with a synchronized flag should be used to extract data in a measurement.

6.2 Magnitude units

The IEC 61869-9 enforce the use of integer values using 0.001 A and 0.01 V as units, so the software should use these units to interpret the raw data coming in the SV stream. Additionally, to recover the input signal, the software has to take into account also the transform ratio configured in the SAMU.

6.3 Parameter extraction from waveform

The software should recover at least amplitude and absolute phase from the values coming in the SV stream, because these parameters should be compared with the input to obtain magnitude and phase displacement in for all the points listed in the standard. Additionally, to amplitude and phase, it is recommended to report the reconstructed frequency and offset of the output waveform. These parameters help to detect possible errors in the input settings or the signal chain. A discussion of the possible algorithms to be used for those purposes and their corresponding uncertainties has been developed in the frame this project as deliverable D3 [12].

7 Advices for SV processing and calibration algorithms in amplitude and phase displacement

The following is a simple guide to be considered when processing Sampled Values (SVs) for the calibration of SAMUs.

Figure 2. Advices for SV processing and calibration algorithms in amplitude and phase displacement.

- Verify that the SVs on the network are synchronized. This can be done using Wireshark by checking that `SV.smpSync = 2`.
- Use traffic analysis tools such as TSHARK or TCPDUMP to identify the parameters required by the signal processing algorithms. These tools must be configured to recognize the destination MAC address of the SAMU being calibrated. The parameters to be extracted and stored by the traffic analyzer are:
 - APP-ID, SVID
 - `smpCnt`
 - Timestamp
 - Dataset and measured values
 - Using the trace parameters, verify the sampling rate.
 - Determine which SAMU channel will be calibrated.
- Select the algorithm to be used for signal reconstruction from SVs. Several algorithms have been developed in the WP2 of the Digital-IT project, as explained in the corresponding [12].
- Most laboratories participating in this task used a 4-parameter Sine fitting method to calculate phase and amplitude. Therefore, the trace captured with TSHARK or TCPDUMP from the SAMU to be calibrated must be fitted accordingly so that the signal reconstruction algorithm can use it.
- If performing a comparison-based calibration, compare the original signal with the digitized signal obtained from the algorithm and calculate both the error and the uncertainty.

7.1 Real-time capturing and processing of sample values

An alternative to using traffic analysis tools and offline processing of captured data is to use real-time capturing and processing. However, this will have performance requirements on both computer hardware and software.

The approach can be used with both high-level programming tools such as LabVIEW or low-level programming using C, C++ or Rust.

The challenging part is the acquisition of ethernet frames from the network interface. The sample value packets are data link layer (Layer 2) packets that can be acquired from the network interface using open-source libraries such as libpcap (www.tcpdump.org) for both Windows and Linux or low-level raw socket reads on Linux. The libpcap library can be used on LabVIEW for Windows using a dynamic linked library (DLL). The library is the same as the one used in the traffic analysis tools mentioned above.

The main steps for a real-time application are:

1. Raw packet acquisition from network interface
2. Packet filtering using APP-ID
3. Packet decoding to sample value data
4. Sample value buffering to suitable window length
5. Sample value processing

To accomplish this in real time threaded programming is normally needed. One option is to have separate threads for packet acquisition, decoding and processing. Performance is most critical when using high-level programs. For example, a high-level program can be limited to acquiring and processing one sample value stream at a time while low-level programs can handle multiple streams. From our experience, using LabVIEW on Windows on a standard laptop computer we are limited to analyzing one sample value stream at a time. With low-level programs using Rust, we can handle tens of streams on the same computer. This requires of course that the processing algorithms are also implemented in an efficient way. However, a large disadvantage with low-level programming is the lack of libraries for computing and visualization.

7.2 Example of four-parameter sine fitting method (python and LabVIEW)

An example of using the four-parameter sine fitting method to calculate the amplitude and phase displacement is this:

$$s = a \sin(2\pi ft + p) + d$$

Where the fitted parameters are:

- a , amplitude in volt or ampere, initial guess half of peak to peak of signal
- f , frequency, initial guess nominal value
- p , phase displacement, initial guess zero
- d , offset, mean of signal

and t is the time calculated from the sample count. The RMS value is calculated by dividing the amplitude by the square root of two. This method can be implemented using python and making use of the `scipy.optimize.curve_fit` function from the Python library SciPy (scipy.org) to perform the fitting.

The input to the fit-function besides the model above are two vectors with timestamps, in seconds, and the measured signal waveform. The signal window has been normally ten periods of the nominal frequency. This analysis method requires that the signal is stable, that is the fitted parameters are constant, within the window and that signal is a pure sinusoidal signal without any other frequency components. The fitting method has been used as a post analysis method on saved waveforms.

In cases where the signal is not a pure sinusoidal signal, another algorithm can be used based on resampling. In some cases they were used in LabVIEW and the steps are:

1. Sample the signal for more than ten periods
2. Use the function **Extract Single Tone Information VI** to find the fundamental frequency
3. Resample the signal for exactly ten periods based on the calculated frequency using **Interpolate 1D VI with the cubic Hermite option**
4. Calculate the frequency spectrum using **Amplitude and Phase Spectrum VI**

RMS values and phase displacements can then be extracted for the fundamental and harmonics of the signal. This algorithm also requires that the signal is “static” during the evaluated window, ten periods in our case. The analysis has been done in real time in a program that acquires and process data from one sample value stream at a time.

8 Other Sampled Values enabled equipment

8.1 Instrument transformer test bridges

As the name implies, an instrument transformer bridge is used for testing VTs and CTs for their scale factor and phase displacement errors. Nowadays, some bridges also facilitate testing instrument transformers and SAMUs, which implement a digital SV output according to IEC 61869-9 [5]. Generally, bridges are tested by purposefully generating known errors in their inputs. As bridge reading should faithfully present this error, a calibrated bridge error is then the deviation from the expected error. In a conventional bridge this is done by feeding the bridge with two voltage or current signals, with variable magnitude ratio and phase displacement. In a digital bridge the approach is somewhat different. The other signal is replaced by an SV stream from the reference equipment. Errors are generated by introducing errors in the stream.

An example test setup for calibrating test bridges with SV input is shown Figure 3. Scaling devices other than those used for converting the bridge input values to suit reference equipment are here omitted, since the setups are used only for calibrating bridges, which often have inputs for standardized current and voltage secondaries, e.g. $100/\sqrt{3}$ V and 1 A or 5 A, or have similar input ranges. Thus, the same analog test signal is connected to the bridge and to the reference measurement chain. In this case, it is typical to use only a single signal, since often the bridges support only one input. In the case of more than one input the same test signal can be connected to all inputs if the signal source allows. The bridge under calibration may have an option to select which signal in the stream it uses as a digital input. If this is not the case, the correct input channel in the reference device must be used or the device must in some other way be set up to populate the correct quantity in the SV stream.

Figure 3. An example setup for calibrating test bridges with SV data input.

The reference measurement chain (reference device, current and voltage transducers) is calibrated and adjusted to produce an SV stream, which reflects the input quantity. Its gain error has been accounted for in the output SV stream magnitude and its phase error has been compensated by adjusting the sample clock phase with respect to 1PPS. To facilitate this, a time interval counter is used in the setup in Figure 3. When the phasor value of the signal in the SV stream is correct, the bridge reading reflects the error of the bridge and can be considered as the calibration result with the exception that the sign of the reading should be

changed. As an example, if a scale factor reading from the bridge is 0.01 %, it means that the bridge is measuring -0.01 % error between its analog input and the signal embedded into the SV stream. For clarity, the reading and the error should be documented in a calibration certificate.

Test bridges are used for verifying the conformance of LPITs and SAMUs to their stated accuracy class limits under various operating conditions. The accuracy classes, together with their error limits with various input magnitudes, are given in the IEC 61869 [5] family of standards. A thorough calibration of a test bridge includes verification of its ability to determine the error of an LPIT or SAMU for the range of their permissible errors. To accomplish this, errors are added in the reference device SV stream to simulate a non-ideal LPIT being tested by the bridge. The scale factor of the reference device is changed for creating a ratio error. Sample clock delay w.r.t. 1PPS and possibly the *SmpCnt* value immediately following 1PPS is adjusted for generating a phase displacement. Table 9 shows example measurements on the first seven rows, where the “SV stream error” column shows the purposefully added errors in the SV stream. Relevant standards should be consulted to determine the range of errors applicable to the targeted class of LPITs and SAMUs.

The 1 mA and 10 mV LSB values in the SV stream may cause a measurement error, especially in the magnitude value encoded into the SV stream. A simple and effective workaround is to use a large scale factor in the reference device and in the device under calibration. While it is impossible to tell what kind of algorithm the bridge runs to extract phasor data from the input SV stream, a simple test can be performed where the artificial scale factor is varied, and bridge error is observed. If differences can be seen when increasing the scale factor, a saturating error from the bridge reading will signify a high enough value. This is shown in TABLE on lines 8 through 12.

Table 9. An example of a table in a calibration certificate, where various sv stream impairments are introduced.

Line	Settings		SV stream error		DUC reading		DUC error	
	Input quantities [V] / [Hz]	Reference & DUC scale factor	Magnitude	Phase displacement	Magnitude	Phase displacement	Magnitude	Phase displacement
			[%]	[min]	[%]	[min]	[%]	[min]
1	60 / 50	10000	0.000	0	0.001	0	-0.001	0
2	60 / 50	10000	0.100	0	0.101	0	-0.001	0
3	60 / 50	10000	0.200	0	0.204	0	-0.004	0
4	60 / 50	10000	0.300	0	0.307	0	-0.007	0
5	60 / 50	10000	0.000	10	0.001	9	-0.001	-1
6	60 / 50	10000	0.000	20	0.001	18	-0.001	-2
7	60 / 50	10000	0.000	30	0.001	27	-0.001	-3
8	60 / 50	1	0.000	0	0.010	5	-0.010	5
9	60 / 50	10	0.000	0	0.005	2	-0.005	2
10	60 / 50	100	0.000	0	0.002	1	-0.002	1
11	60 / 50	1000	0.000	0	0.001	0	-0.001	0
12	60 / 50	10000	0.000	0	0.001	0	-0.001	0

8.2 Electricity meters with SV input

IEC TC 13 will soon release a standard for the requirements and test conditions for electricity meters, which use SV data as input instead of analog signals. The envisaged accuracy class for the meter will be 0.01D, where the “D” stands for digital, emphasizing most importantly, that the device is digital-only and will only do calculation using data measured by other instruments on a substation.

The preferred test method thus involves feeding the meter with an SV stream, where the active power is known with a low enough uncertainty. Two test methods are possible, as drawn in Figure 4 and Figure 5. In Figure 4, an analog test setup is augmented with a calibrated SAMU. The obvious problem with this approach is the stringent requirement for SV test signal generation. The analog source providing the test signals together with

the SAMU should have a combined uncertainty in the 0.001 % range, which can be challenging. A better approach is shown in Figure 5, where an SV data generator is used for simulating an SV stream, which is fed to the meter under test. Since the test setup now has no components, which should be calibrated, the uncertainty analysis of the calibration is simplified, since all relevant uncertainty components stem from the meter itself. Uncertainties related to the meter reading should be considered, including the deviation of the impulse output, or in case of DLMS, the limited resolution of the energy register for a given energy quantum.

Figure 4. SV input energy meter calibration setup using an analog signals source and a SAMU.

Figure 5. SV input energy meter calibration setup using a synthetic SV data source.

The test signals should be generated according to the following formula:

$$x_p(n) = X_p \sqrt{2} \sin(2\pi f t_n + \varphi_p) + x_{p \text{ res}}(n),$$

where x_p is a 32-bit signed integer according to IEC 61869-9 rules for LSB magnitude, X_p is the RMS value of the primary signal, when $y_{p \text{ res}}(n) = 0$, f is the signal frequency, φ_p is the primary phase, $x_{p \text{ res}}(n)$ is the primary residual signal including harmonic, sub-harmonic, inter-harmonic and DC components and noise. n is the data sample counter, and t_n is the effective time where the primary signal (current or voltage) of the n^{th} data set has been sampled. f , X_p , and φ_p are constant for steady-state conditions. With instantaneous magnitude values presented by 32-bit integers, which provide orders of magnitude of precision especially for nominal magnitudes, the only other uncertainty component to consider is the power factor.

9 Conclusion

The transition from analog to digital instrumentation in electrical substations represents a fundamental shift in how voltage and current measurements are acquired, processed, and communicated. Sampled Value (SV)-enabled devices, such as stand-alone merging units (SAMUs), are at the core of this transformation, offering real-time, synchronized, and interoperable measurement data in accordance with IEC 61850 and IEC 61869 standards.

This work compiles information from six laboratories that have carried out the calibration of a commercial SAMU using different testbeds and obtained compatible results. As a result, a Good Practice Guide is presented with the aim of establishing consistent and traceable calibration procedures for commercial SV-enabled instrumentation.

- One of the key aspects to highlight is the grounding of input channels, which is essential to ensure that no common-mode voltage is present on the current inputs, avoiding ground loops and leakage of measurement current to ground, as these issues can affect calibration accuracy.

- The capture and processing of SVs can be performed using high- or low-level programming tools. For the development of this work, tools and libraries such as TSHARK, TCPDUMP, LabVIEW, C, C++, Python, and Rust have been used.
- The selection of the signal reconstruction algorithm must consider that if the source signal is not purely sinusoidal, it is more appropriate to use a resampling-based algorithm rather than a sine-fitting approach.
- Uncertainty estimation is a critical factor in calibration procedures. Therefore, this work presents five different approaches to uncertainty calculation.

The guidelines presented herein are intended to ensure that digital measurement systems in substations deliver reliable performance, maintain measurement traceability, and meet the stringent requirements of modern grid operation. They also support the broader goal of facilitating interoperability between devices from different vendors, which is a key enabler for scalable and future-proof digital substations.

Appendix A: Testbeds description and uncertainty estimation

A.1 Calibration setup of CIRCE

At CIRCE, a testbed has been developed with two configurations: amplitude calibration and phase displacement calibration. In both configurations, the main IED is the SAMU, which is shared with the rest of the laboratories. The "Meinberg LANTIME M10000" clock is responsible for synchronizing the SAMU through the Pulse-per-second (1PPS) signal and the *Network Time Protocol* (NTP) to the server where the Calibration software runs. The "Hirschmann Greyhound 1040" switch with IEC/IEEE 61850-9-3 [9] "Power Profile" configuration is used to interconnect all the IEDs in both configurations.

Figure 6. CIRCE testbed for amplitude calibration

Current and voltage signals are generated using the "Fluke 5502E Calibrator" and routed directly to the analogue inputs of the SAMU for the case of amplitude calibration, as shown in Figure 6. The Calibrator" generates a sinusoidal signal, which is digitized by the SAMU and then published to the network via SV. These SV are acquired, processed, and checked by the Calibration software, which is responsible for reconstructing

the signal and calculating the amplitude. The digitization error and its uncertainty are computed using the testbed's known generation patterns and uncertainties.

Figure 7. CIRCE testbed for phase calibration

Figure 7 shows the configuration for phase displacement calibration. In this testbed, current and voltage signals are generated using the "Omicron CMC 356" and connected directly to the analogue inputs of the SAMU. The connection to the "NI_PXI-6363" digitizer card is made through attenuation circuits that ensure operation within the card's dynamic range. The analogue signal is connected in parallel with the voltage attenuation circuit and in series with the current attenuation resistor. Three programs were developed to enable the processing of SV, process the signal digitized by the "NI_PXI-6363", calculate its absolute phase using the rising edge of the 1PPS and calculate the phase shift and uncertainty of the SAMU's generation.

- Traceability. Voltage and current magnitude measurements are traceable via calibration of the reference instrument. The uncertainty is presented in Table 10.
- Physical connection of current and voltage inputs. The calibration was carried out phase by phase, meaning only the phase to be calibrated for current or voltage was connected to the generator.

Table 10. Uncertainty (U_c) for measurements of current and voltage, magnitude and phase displacement (circe testbed)

Magnitude				Phase displacement	
U_c of the reference for current ($k=2$)		U_c of the reference for voltage ($k=2$)		U_c for phase displacement ($k=2$)	
Input %	%	Input %	%	Input Frequency (Hz)	(deg)
1,25-2,5	0,02	2-5	0,04	50	0,072
5-120	0,03	10-20	0,03	650	0,936
-	-	30-120	0,02	-	-

Inputs are in % of rated current (1A) and rated voltage (120V)

A.2 Calibration setup of VTT

VTT's setup for calibrating equipment with SV data output is shown in Figure 8. VTT's calibration approach is based on comparing the magnitude and phase displacement in two SV streams, which are based on the same analog signals fed to the device under calibration (DUC) and the reference device (REF). The reference device is an in-house designed digitizer, which is calibrated for its gain and 1PPS referenced absolute input delay. The input delay calibration ensures that the phase displacement of the signals encoded into the SV stream are correctly aligned with 1PPS and can thus be used as a reference. The digitizer supports all SV stream formats in IEC 61869-9 [5].

Figure 8. VTT's setup for calibrating devices with SV data output.

Test signals are generated using a 1-phase or a 3-phase source. The 1-phase source consist of a function generator and respectively a voltage amplifier and a transconductance amplifier to generate voltage and current test signals up to 500 V and 20 A. The single-phase source can be used for doing all tests in IEC 61869-1 and -13. The reference measurement path consists of a set of shunts of various values to convert the test current to voltage and a 1:50 voltage divider. SV streams are connected to a PC (not drawn) via a utility grade switch. The PC is used for capturing the SV streams into .cSV files using Wireshark after which they are post processed to extract the DUC SV stream error.

Timing signals are supplied by a PTPv2 Grandmaster clock, which itself is synchronized by GPS. Utility profile according to IEC 61850-9-3 is used for all time links and the switch is setup in boundary clock mode. The reference device uses 1PPS for synchronization, which is supplied by the Grandmaster via a edge drive amplifier to generate a fast-rising 1PPS signal to reduce timing uncertainty. 1PPS signal for the DUC is also supplied by the edge drive amplifier. To compensate the reference device input latency, its sample clock is shifted in time with respect to 1PPS. A time interval counter is used for comparing the reference device sample clock phase w.r.t. 1PPS during calibration. In case the DUC uses PTPv2 for synchronicity, the boundary clock switch is calibrated for its internal error using the absolute calibration method described in Digital-IT [13].

The same setup can be used also for calibrating devices that have an input for SV data, such as instrument transformer and SAMU test bridges. A test bridge is used for comparing the magnitude and phase displacement of an analog test signals to their digital presentations as SV streams. The setup to do this is shown in Figure 9. The calibrated stream from the reference device (REF) is now input into the bridge (DUC). Since the reference stream is calibrated, any error displayed by the bridge is the error of the bridge itself. The setup only supports 1PPS synchronization, since test bridges with PTPv2 support are not available at the moment.

Figure 9. VTT's setup for calibrating devices with SV data input.

Uncertainty budgets for the reference measurement chain are derived for 50 Hz and 650 Hz for a single-phase calibration. The magnitude and phase displacement uncertainty budgets are given in Table 11 and Table 12.

Reference device timing uncertainty is given as nanoseconds and converted into corresponding phase displacement uncertainty value for the two frequencies. Same applies for an electrical to optical 1PPS converter, which may be needed to supply a 1PPS signal via optical fiber to device under calibration. Type A uncertainty is produced by the calibration software based on the deviation of magnitude and phase in the data streams and should be added on top of the type B uncertainty of the reference measurement chain.

Table 11. Magnitude uncertainty for the reference measurement chain (VTT testbed).

ITEM	Voltage		Current	
	< 10 %	>= 10 %	< 10 %	>= 10 %
Input magnitude % of nominal				
Input 50 Hz TOTAL [%], $k = 2$	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04
Input 650 Hz TOTAL [%], $k = 2$	n/a	n/a	n/a	0.04

Table 12. phase displacement uncertainty for the reference measurement chain (VTT testbed).

ITEM	Voltage		Current	
	< 10 %	>= 10 %	< 10	>= 10
Input magnitude % of nominal				
Input 50 Hz TOTAL [deg], $k = 2$	0.002	0.004	0.007	0.006
Input 650 Hz TOTAL [deg], $k = 2$	n/a	n/a	n/a	0.02

- Magnitude calibration was performed using a single test signal and the voltage and current inputs were connected respective in parallel and in series. For phase displacement, the voltage input calibration was carried out using a true 3-phase voltage signal and the current inputs were calibrated by connecting all the inputs in series.

A.3 Calibration setup of RISE

Figure 10 shows a diagram of the setup for calibration in the frequency range 50 – 2000 Hz. This setup is a calibration system composed by a current and voltage generation system and a measurement system for magnitude and phase displacement. The generation and the magnitude measurement systems might include different instruments depending on the frequency of the current or voltage.

The sample value output from the SAMU is connected to a switch, sw, where also a computer, PC2, is connected to acquire and process the sample values. The SAMU is calibrated by comparison of the magnitude and phase displacement calculated from the SAMUs readings with the calibration system’s readings.

Figure 10. Setup for calibration of SAMU in the frequency range 50 – 2000 Hz.

- **Generation system**

It consists of a controller, a 16-bit digital-to-analogue converter (DAC) and an amplifying stage. The instrument used for signal amplification depends on the frequency of the current or voltage to measure. PC1 is used to communicate with the controller and set the parameters of the signal to generate.

- **Time reference**

The time reference and the phase displacement measurement system are the same for all the setup variations. As shown in Figure 10, both the reference measurement system and the SAMU are synchronised using a 1PPS signal. The 1PPS signal originates from the official Swedish time scale UTC(SP) and is calibrated at a reference plane, the fiber connector (SC), at the input of the SAMU. The reference phase displacement measurement system is then calibrated against UTC(SP). The measured delay is 98 ns with an uncertainty of 30 ns ($k = 1$).

- **Reference phase displacement measurement**

The reference phase displacement measurement system is presented in Figure 10 and consists of highly accurate voltage dividers and current shunts, a 16 bit analogue-to-digital converter (ADC), and a controller for the acquisition of the signals. The controller receives the reference 1PPS signal. PC1 communicates with the controller, receives the data, calculates the phase-angle of the current and voltage signals, and displays the results in degrees with respect to the 1PPS signal. The reference phase displacement measurement system is then calibrated against UTC(SP). The measured delay is 98 ns with an uncertainty of 30 ns ($k = 1$).

The uncertainty for voltage and current phase displacement measurements is given in Table 13. The model equation is:

$$\varepsilon = \phi_{DUT} - \phi_{REF} \quad [\%]$$

Where ε , ϕ_{DUT} , and ϕ_{REF} are the error in phase displacement (of the current or voltage signal) of the device under test (DUT), the phase displacement read by the DUT, and the phase displacement read by the reference

instrument, respectively. Calibration of SAMU for frequencies up to 650 Hz has been done so far with this setup. The uncertainty budget includes the contributions of the SAMU.

Table 13. Uncertainty budget for calibration of samu in voltage and current phase displacement.

	Current 1.25 – 120 % %, 50 Hz (deg)	Voltage 2 – 120 % %, 50 Hz (deg)	Current 100 % %, 100 – 650 Hz (ns)
Expanded uncertainty	0.046 ($k = 2.87, v_{eff} = 4$)	0.005 ($k = 2.65, v_{eff} = 5$)	191 ns ($k = 2$)

When $k = 2$, the expanded uncertainty has been evaluated using a normal distribution. When $k > 2$, the expanded uncertainty has been evaluated using a Student’s t-distribution with v_{eff} effective degrees of freedom.

- **Calibration of magnitude of current and voltage**

This setup is shown Figure 10. The amplifying stage is given by the instrument Omicron CMS 356 whose outputs are three voltages and three currents. Traceability for voltage and current magnitude is given by the instrument ZERA COM 5003, which has in turn been calibrated by comparison to RISE’s references for RMS current and voltage. This instrument receives directly three voltage and three current signals in the magnitude range of interest of this project.

The uncertainty for voltage and current magnitude measurements using this setup is given in Table 14. Uncertainty (U_c) for measurements of current and voltage magnitude (RISE testbed). The model equation is:

$$\varepsilon = 100 \cdot \frac{I_{DUT} - I_{REF}}{I_{REF}} \quad [\%]$$

Where ε , I_{DUT} , and I_{REF} are the error in current magnitude of the device under test (DUT), the current magnitude read by the DUT, and the current magnitude read by the reference instrument, respectively. An analogous model equation is used for the voltage. Calibration of SAMU for frequencies up to 650 Hz has been done so far with this setup. The uncertainty budget includes the contributions of the SAMU.

Table 14. Uncertainty (U_c) for measurements of current and voltage magnitude (RISE testbed)

	Current 1.25 % %, 50 Hz	Current 2 – 10 % %, 50 Hz	Current 20 – 120 % %, 50 Hz	Voltage 2 – 120 % %, 50 Hz	Current 100 % %, 100 – 650 Hz
Expanded uncertainty (k = 2)	0.055 %	0.043 %	0.021 %	0.017 %	0.041 %

The calibration was carried out in three-phase connection for the DUT’s channels 1-3, and with the channel 4 voltage input connected in parallel with channel 3 and the current channel 4 connected in series with channel 3.

A.4 Calibration setup of VSL

Figure 11. shows the diagram of the SAMU calibration setup at VSL. The key components in this setup are, a timing reference, a signal generation system, a distribution system, and a commercial wattmeter used as a

reference instrument. A PC is used to collect all data from either the SV enabled devices and the reference meter and analysis the incoming data using various algorithms developed within the project.

Figure 11. VSL Setup for calibration of SAMU, showing the reference instrument and the SAMU connected in parallel to the generator. The time reference is distributed through the switch to the key components. The PC is used to control the setup and collect all data.

Either a single or multi-phase power calibrator is used for the generation of the voltage and current depending on the calibration requirements. The distribution board is used to distribute the voltage and current to the different devices. The phases can be connected in parallel (voltage) and series (current) or supplied separately to emulate a 3-phase system.

- Time reference.** The frequency and time reference for the setup is derived from a PTP master clock, which is locked to UTC(VSL) via 10 MHz and 1PPS signals. The PTP service is distributed via a PTP-aware switch using the 2017 Power profile. All equipment is synchronised to this reference.
- Reference instrument.** The reference instrument can either be a calibrated SAMU or a reference watt meter. Both are capable of measuring current and voltage and synchronize its readings to PTP signals. For this setup a Yokogawa WT5000 reference watt meter is used which is capable of timestamping with an accuracy of 250 ns. It can measure up to 7 current and voltage signals with a sampling rate of up to 2 MHz
- Traceability.** Voltage and current magnitude measurements are traceable via the reference instrument. The reference instrument is calibrated for magnitude and absolute phase. The phase is made traceable by measuring the reference 1PPS passed through a slew rate limiter to one of its voltage inputs. A fitting technique is used to determine the inter-sample time from which the absolute time delay can be calculated.

The uncertainty is presented in TABLE 15

TABLE 15. Vsl uncertainty budget (VSL testbed)

Uncertainty component	Magnitude	Phase
Reference device @ 50Hz Voltage and Current	0.011%	0.00225
Switch PTP delay		0.00036
Total (k=2)	0.022%	0.0052

- The calibration was carried out for voltage and current separately. While calibrating the voltage channels, the current channels were disconnected and vice versa. This approach was taken to prevent crosstalk between the voltage and current channels, which has been observed to give errors in the calibration. The voltage channels were connected in parallel and the current channels in series for ease of measurement. A check was performed with a poly phase setup, no significant deviations have been observed.

A.5 Calibration setup of GUM

Figure 12 shows the stand for calibrating the voltage part of the SAMU, and Figure 13 shows the stand for calibrating the current part of the SAMU. The stand was built jointly by GUM and ITR from devices belonging to them.

Figure 12. Setup for calibration voltage SAMU

Figure 13. Setup for calibration current SAMU

The voltage and current sources are calibrators such as the CMC356 Omicron, Fluke 5520A or 5725A. They were selected due to the possibility of synchronization with a PTP time server. The signal from the time server is distributed to all devices included in the station using a Ticro 100 converter. This converter allows for sending a PPS and 10 MHz signal. The reference standard is a Zera measuring bridge type WM3000U. It is used in both the voltage and current systems. In the current system, to obtain a voltage signal, which is necessary as a reference signal for the WM3000U bridge, precise shunts type A40B Fluke were used. For each current value, an appropriate shunt is used. In the uncertainty budget presented in Table 16 and Table 17, the limit values of errors of the reference devices were adopted: the bridge and the shunts.

Table 16. Uncertainty budget for calibration voltage samu

Uncertainty Component	Distribution	%	min
Standard deviation of mean	Normal	0,0001	0,0
Bridge WM3000U specification	Rectangular	0,0115	0,9
Combine uncertainty	$k=1$	0,012	0,9
Expanded uncertainty	$k=2$	0,023	1,7

Table 17. Uncertainty budget for calibration current samu

Uncertainty Component	Distribution	%	min
Standard deviation of mean	Normal	0,0001	0,0
Bridge WM3000U specification	Rectangular	0,0115	0,9
A40B spec. (Resistance + ACDC transfer)	Rectangular	0,0022	0,2
Combine uncertainty	$k=1$	0,012	0,9
Expanded Uncertainty	$k=2$	0,024	1,8

A.6 Calibration setup of Metrosert

The measurement setup developed at Metrosert, shown in Figure 14, consists of a Fluke 8588A DMM as a reference, a device under test (DUT), a voltage and current source (U&I Source), and a master clock. Three types of synchronization signals referenced to the frequency standard are available: PPS, 10 MHz, and PTP. In digitizing mode, the DMM supports input values of up to 742 V and 21 A (RMS). A Fluke 5730A multifunction calibrator, along with a current amplifier, serves as the voltage and current source. The calibrator is synchronized to the common PPS signal using a function generator connected to the “phase lock-in” BNC connector on its rear panel, injecting a phase-locking signal at the test frequency. The function generator is ultimately aligned with the PPS signal. The absolute phase error of the source is not critical as it functions as a non-reference device. Additionally, the function generator and the DMM can be optionally clocked together using a common 10 MHz reference.

Calibration of the DMM's voltage ranges (100 mV to 1000 V) and current ranges (1 mA to 10 A) follows a standard procedure using either a characterized multifunction calibrator or a Fluke 792A AC-DC transfer standard in combination with a set of cage-type AC-DC current shunts. The absolute phase error of the DMM is determined using a digital phase comparator at 1 V, followed by a step-up procedure with precision voltage dividers to extend the calibration up to 740 V. To characterize the phase error of the DMM across its current measurement ranges, a set of eleven precision current shunts is employed. The measurement setup and characterization of the reference DMM are described in more detail in a paper accepted for publication in IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement [14].

For the magnitude and phase errors of the most accurate Class 0.05 SAMUs, the TUR exceeds 6:1 at all measurement points, in accordance with [4].

Figure 14. Block diagram of the measurement setup developed at Metroser for the calibration of the SAMU.

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